

Machine learning based prognosis prediction of intracerebral hemorrhage outcome and counterfactual analysis on treatment effectiveness of surgical intervention

Eunhye Yang^{1,2}, Kay-Cheong Teo³, Gary K K Lau^{3,4}, Joshua W K Ho^{1,2}

¹ School of Biomedical Sciences, The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

jwkho@hku.hk

² Laboratory of Data Discovery for Health Limited (D²4H), Hong Kong Science Park, Hong Kong

³ Division of Neurology, Department of Medicine, The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

⁴ State Key Laboratory of Brain and Cognitive Science, The University of Hong Kong

Abstract. Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) continues to have high morbidity and mortality despite the development of numerous surgical interventions such as clot evacuation (CE) and external ventricular drain (EVD). Early prognosis and appropriate clinical decisions remain to be the most effective in improving outcomes, with real-world treatment effectiveness of surgical operations being hard to quantify due to the lack of feasibility of randomized controlled trials. We collected a large retrospective dataset of 870 ICH patients in Hong Kong consisting of their demographical, clinical, radiological, and neurological findings at admission and clinical outcome in 6-months. Using this dataset, we built a prognosis prediction machine learning (ML) system that classifies the 6-month outcome more accurately than standard prognosis score such as ICH score. Through feature selection of the ML system, we were able to identify novel core features associated with prognostic ability, including the sub-scores of Glasgow Coma Scale, admission pulse rate, and Graeb score. Furthermore, using various ML techniques such as logistic regression, weighted least square, Random Forest feature selection and the prognosis prediction model from this study, we developed a causal inference strategy that emulates a target trial to estimate effectiveness of CE and EVD using our data set. The results suggested a significant benefit of the operations on 6-month ICH outcome. Our study provides a framework of using observational electronic medical records for prognosis prediction and estimation of treatment effectiveness.

Keywords: Target trial emulation, Machine learning, Causal inference, Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH).

1 Dataset

This study investigated a retrospective dataset of 870 ICH patients admitted to the University of Hong Kong stroke registry from January 2011 to December 2022, of which

88 patients and 36 patients have gone through CE and EVD respectively. The outcome of the patients is measured 6-months after the hospital admission, quantified using modified Rankin Score (mRS), as well as prognostic ICH score. The dataset includes a total of 24 patient features were recorded. For a better balance of the mRS outcome of the samples for prognosis prediction model training, the 6-month outcomes were recategorized into good (mRS 0-2), bad (mRS 3-5) and death.

2 Prognosis prediction model

The prognosis prediction model was built by training an XGBoost classifier by randomly splitting the 746 non-surgery patient samples into training and testing sets to 8:2 ratio. Of the 24 features recorded, 22 prognostic features selected by clinicians were used to train the classifier. The two features not included are Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) and supratentorial/infratentorial location of the hematoma. These two features are replaced with E, V, M sub-scores of GCS and detailed anatomical location of the hematoma instead. The model was finetuned through 10-fold cross validation grid search on training dataset. Performance summary of the model is visualized in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Model performance summary obtained from hold-out test.

For a thorough comparison of the model performance to the conventional ICH prognosis score, another XGBoost classifier was trained on the same set of training dataset. The conventional model was trained only on the 14 features of ICH score. The performances of both models were compared via 10-fold cross validation on held-out testing dataset (Table 1).

Comparing the performance of the two models, the new model trained on 22 prognostic features has statistically significant better performance over the conventional ICH score on all evaluation scores except AUROC for mRS 6 (Table 1).

Table 1. Prognosis model comparison

<i>Evaluation score</i>	<i>Conventional prognostic feature model</i>	<i>New prognostic feature model</i>	<i>p-value</i>
<i>Accuracy</i>	0.75	0.79	2.482e-05
<i>Precision</i>	0.76	0.80	0.002034
<i>Recall</i>	0.75	0.78	3.237e-05
<i>AUROC (mRS 0-2)</i>	0.92	0.93	0.0001694
<i>AUROC (mRS 3-5)</i>	0.81	0.84	4.036e-05
<i>AUROC (mRS 6)</i>	0.95	0.95	0.05768

2.1 Feature importance analysis

Feature importance analysis and identification was facilitated via default feature importance attribute of the trained model summarized in Fig. 1. The feature extraction uncovered some novel features associated with ICH prognosis, including the three subscores of Glasgow Coma Scale, admission pulse rate and Graeb score (Fig. 2). While a few features also included in the conventional prognosis score such as age and largest ICH volume had some importance in prognosis prediction, most features identified by the prognosis model were not included in the conventional ICH prognosis scores (Fig. 2). Additionally, features such as diastolic blood pressure and medical history of diabetes mellitus were not found to be significant at all with the presence of new prognosis features (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Feature importance of the new prognosis model. All features deemed to be significant in outcome prognosis are listed and ranked according to its importance. The feature importances sums up to 1. Other features with importance of 0 are not included in the figure.

2.2 Counterfactual analysis of ICH patients who underwent surgical treatments

Using the prognosis prediction model summarized in Fig. 1, the 6-month outcome of each treated patients were predicted under a simulated reality in which the patients had not received the surgical intervention. The counterfactual analysis results reveal the contribution of CE and EVD to significant decrease in mortality, whereas not as much in morbidity—with EVD having no morbidity benefit (Fig. 3).

With this counterfactual analysis using our ML model, we were able to compare the effectiveness of CE and EVD using our dataset based on the patients who underwent one of two surgical interventions. The results suggested a significant benefit of the operations on 6-month ICH outcome. Our study provides a framework of using observational electronic medical records for prognosis prediction and estimation of treatment effectiveness.

Fig. 3. Counterfactual analysis confusion matrix. Rows plot the ground truth 6-month outcome the treated patients; columns plot the predicted 6-month outcome of the same patient for a simulated counterfactual reality where patient did not receive the treatment. Values above the diagonal line shows the number of patients who experienced benefit from the surgical intervention and values below the line shows the number of patients who experienced adverse effects from the intervention.

Acknowledgments. This study was funded in part by the InnoHK initiative of the Innovation and Technology Commission of the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region Government.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interest in relation to this study.